

AARSD1, annotated USE, essential exon

ANKRD10, annotated USE, poison exon

DNAJC2, annotated USE, poison exon

DNAJC5, annotated USE, poison exon

Scale
 chr20:
 SF3B4
 XRN2
 coding_junctions
 NMD_junctions
 DNAJC5
 DNAJC5

500 bases

62,562,500

hg19

62,563,000

GUSB, annotated USE, essential exon

hg19

500 bases

65,445,500

65,445,000

65,444,500

trend test: **

ICMT, annotated USE, essential exon

NTMT1, annotated USE, essential 5' splice site

STYXL1, annotated USE, essential exon

TIAL1, annotated USE, poison exon

TM7SF3, annotated USE, essential exon

TRA2A, validated USE, poison exon

hg19

5 kb

23,570,000

23,565,000

Scale

:chr7

EWSR1

HNRNPC

SRSF3

TARDBP

U2AF2

XRN2

coding_junctions

NMD_junctions

TRA2A

TRA2A

TRA2A

TRA2A

TRA2A

URI1, annotated USE, essential exon

WASHC4, annotated USE, poison 3' splice site

ZNF655, annotated USE, poison exon

